

Prospective Life Cycle Assessment Of An Electric Vehicle

Equipped With A Model Magnesium Battery:

Supplementary Information

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RESULTS

Table S1: Cradle-to-gate impacts of manufacturing a 40 kWh Mg-S and LIB battery pack

ILCD			
Category	Impact result		Unit
	LIB	Mg-S	
Acidification	5.19E+01	1.63E+01	molc H+ eq
Climate change	4.83E+03	2.72E+03	kg CO ₂ eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	4.77E+05	9.30E+04	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	3.70E+00	1.16E+00	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	1.52E-03	5.00E-04	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	7.77E-03	1.08E-03	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	5.13E-03	4.90E-04	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	1.17E+03	1.41E+02	kBq U235 eq
Land use	2.40E+03	1.51E+03	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	6.73E+00	3.01E+00	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.81E+00	4.71E-01	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	3.90E-04	1.50E-04	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.88E+00	6.28E+00	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	1.74E+01	1.10E+01	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	5.98E+01	3.07E+01	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	6.45E+03	1.83E+03	m ³ water eq
CML-baseline			
Category	Impact result		Unit

	LIB	Mg-S	
Abiotic depletion	5.60E-01	7.97E-02	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	5.63E+04	3.29E+04	MJ
CML-non baseline			
Category	Impact result		Unit
	LIB	Mg-S	
Abiotic depletion (elem., econ. reserve)	3.31E+00	8.37E-01	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (elem., reserve base)	1.71E+00	4.67E-01	kg Sb eq

Table S2: Life cycle impacts of driving 1 km with an ICEV under different fuel and driving style scenarios

ILCD						
Category	Baseline	B20 Diesel	B100 Diesel	City	Highway	Unit
Acidification	6.21E-04	7.29E-04	1.19E-03	7.27E-04	5.81E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	1.86E-01	1.80E-01	1.54E-01	1.95E-01	1.83E-01	kg CO ₂ eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	1.02E+00	1.14E+00	1.68E+00	1.06E+00	1.00E+00	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	1.37E-05	1.72E-05	3.19E-05	1.44E-05	1.35E-05	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	4.41E-09	5.09E-09	8.03E-09	4.84E-09	4.25E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	2.32E-08	4.31E-08	1.29E-07	2.42E-08	2.29E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	9.18E-08	8.15E-08	3.78E-08	1.18E-07	8.21E-08	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	1.74E-02	1.61E-02	1.06E-02	2.12E-02	1.60E-02	kBq U235 eq
Land use	5.79E-01	2.60E+00	1.13E+01	7.29E-01	5.24E-01	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	1.71E-04	3.25E-04	9.90E-04	1.84E-04	1.66E-04	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	2.86E-06	3.47E-06	6.13E-06	3.14E-06	2.76E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	3.75E-08	3.34E-08	1.57E-08	4.86E-08	3.34E-08	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	8.39E-05	8.92E-05	1.12E-04	9.05E-05	8.15E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	5.76E-04	5.95E-04	6.79E-04	6.33E-04	5.55E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	1.86E-03	2.43E-03	4.93E-03	2.00E-03	1.81E-03	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	5.20E-02	5.47E-02	6.73E-02	5.36E-02	5.13E-02	m ³ water eq
CML-baseline						
Category	Baseline	B20 Diesel	B100 Diesel	City	Highway	Unit
Abiotic depletion	5.20E-07	5.97E-07	9.28E-07	5.31E-07	5.16E-07	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	2.56E+00	2.26E+00	9.80E-01	3.40E+00	2.25E+00	MJ
CML-non baseline						
Category	Baseline	B20 Diesel	B100 Diesel	City	Highway	Unit
Abiotic depletion (elem., econ. reserve)	5.96E-06	5.71E-06	4.67E-06	7.13E-06	5.53E-06	kg Sb eq

Abiotic depletion (elem., reserve base)	2.77E-06	2.80E-06	2.94E-06	3.04E-06	2.67E-06	kg Sb eq
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Table S3: Life cycle impacts of driving 1 km with a LIB EV under different electricity and driving style scenarios

ILCD					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Acidification	2.49E-04	2.10E-04	2.97E-04	1.30E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	8.11E-02	6.56E-02	1.00E-01	2.02E-02	kg CO ₂ eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	2.43E+00	1.93E+00	3.04E+00	9.52E-01	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	6.55E-05	5.15E-05	8.26E-05	7.57E-06	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	8.17E-09	6.68E-09	1.00E-08	4.73E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	2.74E-08	2.26E-08	3.33E-08	1.16E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	1.01E-08	9.52E-09	1.09E-08	9.86E-09	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	2.36E-03	2.18E-03	2.58E-03	2.23E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	1.87E-01	1.72E-01	2.04E-01	9.78E-01	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	6.47E-05	5.50E-05	7.67E-05	3.15E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.45E-06	1.18E-06	1.77E-06	1.41E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	5.30E-09	4.57E-09	6.19E-09	2.88E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.89E-05	4.61E-05	5.24E-05	4.44E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	6.18E-04	5.95E-04	6.46E-04	5.50E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	5.95E-04	5.09E-04	6.99E-04	3.20E-04	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	4.49E-02	3.65E-02	5.51E-02	2.67E-02	m3 water eq
CML-baseline					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Abiotic depletion	7.24E-07	5.81E-07	8.98E-07	5.50E-07	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	1.01E+00	8.43E-01	1.22E+00	3.46E-01	MJ
CML-non baseline					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Abiotic depletion (elem., econ. reserve)	2.44E-06	2.02E-06	2.96E-06	2.09E-06	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (elem., reserve base)	1.42E-06	1.15E-06	1.74E-06	1.38E-06	kg Sb eq

Table S4: Life cycle impacts of driving 1 km with a Mg-S EV under different electricity and driving style scenarios

ILCD					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Acidification	2.56E-04	2.20E-04	3.10E-04	1.34E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	8.39E-02	6.75E-02	1.04E-01	2.05E-02	kg CO ₂ eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	2.52E+00	1.99E+00	3.16E+00	9.81E-01	CTUe

Freshwater eutrophication	6.80E-05	5.33E-05	8.60E-05	7.73E-06	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	8.44E-09	6.87E-09	1.04E-08	4.86E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	2.83E-08	2.32E-08	3.44E-08	1.18E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	1.02E-08	9.60E-09	1.10E-08	9.96E-09	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	2.39E-03	2.20E-03	2.62E-03	2.26E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	1.89E-01	1.74E-01	2.08E-01	1.01E+00	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	6.65E-05	5.62E-05	7.90E-05	3.19E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.49E-06	1.21E-06	1.84E-06	1.45E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	5.43E-09	4.66E-09	6.37E-09	2.92E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.94E-05	4.64E-05	5.31E-05	4.48E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	6.22E-04	6.00E-04	6.50E-04	5.49E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	6.10E-04	5.20E-04	7.20E-04	3.19E-04	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	4.64E-02	3.76E-02	5.72E-02	2.75E-02	m3 water eq
CML-baseline					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Abiotic depletion	7.49E-07	5.99E-07	9.32E-07	5.68E-07	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	1.04E+00	8.64E-01	1.26E+00	3.50E-01	MJ
CML-non baseline					
Category	Baseline	City	Highway	Renewable	Unit
Abiotic depletion (elem., econ. reserve)	2.52E-06	2.07E-06	3.07E-06	2.15E-06	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (elem., reserve base)	1.46E-06	1.19E-06	1.80E-06	1.42E-06	kg Sb eq

Table S5 part 1: Life cycle impacts of the Mg-S EV under different efficiency, electricity and energy density scenarios. (ED = Energy density).

Overall efficiency = 0.95 (95%)							
Category	Electricity DE2030						Unit
	100%ED (Baseline)	90%ED	80%ED	70%ED	60%ED	50%ED	
Acidification	2.56E-04	2.58E-04	2.60E-04	2.63E-04	2.68E-04	2.73E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	8.39E-02	8.47E-02	8.56E-02	8.68E-02	8.85E-02	9.08E-02	kg CO2 eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	2.52E+00	2.54E+00	2.57E+00	2.61E+00	2.67E+00	2.74E+00	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	6.80E-05	6.87E-05	6.96E-05	7.07E-05	7.21E-05	7.42E-05	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	8.44E-09	8.51E-09	8.61E-09	8.72E-09	8.88E-09	9.10E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	2.83E-08	2.85E-08	2.88E-08	2.92E-08	2.97E-08	3.04E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	1.02E-08	1.03E-08	1.03E-08	1.03E-08	1.04E-08	1.05E-08	CTUe

Ionizing radiation HH	2.39E-03	2.40E-03	2.41E-03	2.42E-03	2.44E-03	2.47E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	1.89E-01	1.90E-01	1.91E-01	1.92E-01	1.94E-01	1.96E-01	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	6.65E-05	6.70E-05	6.76E-05	6.83E-05	6.94E-05	7.08E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.49E-06	1.51E-06	1.52E-06	1.54E-06	1.57E-06	1.61E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	5.43E-09	5.47E-09	5.51E-09	5.57E-09	5.65E-09	5.75E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.94E-05	4.96E-05	4.97E-05	5.00E-05	5.03E-05	5.07E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	6.22E-04	6.23E-04	6.24E-04	6.26E-04	6.29E-04	6.32E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	6.10E-04	6.14E-04	6.19E-04	6.26E-04	6.35E-04	6.48E-04	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	4.64E-02	4.68E-02	4.73E-02	4.80E-02	4.89E-02	5.01E-02	m3 water eq

Table S5 part 2: Life cycle impacts of the Mg-S EV under different efficiency, electricity and energy density scenarios. (ED = Energy density).

Overall efficiency = 0.95							
Category	Electricity RN						Unit
	100%ED (Baseline)	90%ED	80%ED	70%ED	60%ED	50%ED	
Acidification	1.34E-04	1.35E-04	1.35E-04	1.36E-04	1.38E-04	1.39E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	2.05E-02	2.06E-02	2.07E-02	2.09E-02	2.11E-02	2.13E-02	kg CO2 eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	9.81E-01	9.89E-01	1.00E+00	1.01E+00	1.03E+00	1.05E+00	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	7.73E-06	7.78E-06	7.83E-06	7.91E-06	8.01E-06	8.14E-06	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	4.86E-09	4.90E-09	4.94E-09	5.00E-09	5.07E-09	5.18E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	1.18E-08	1.18E-08	1.19E-08	1.20E-08	1.21E-08	1.23E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	9.96E-09	9.99E-09	1.00E-08	1.01E-08	1.01E-08	1.02E-08	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	2.26E-03	2.26E-03	2.27E-03	2.28E-03	2.30E-03	2.32E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	1.01E+00	1.02E+00	1.03E+00	1.05E+00	1.07E+00	1.10E+00	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	3.19E-05	3.20E-05	3.21E-05	3.23E-05	3.25E-05	3.29E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.45E-06	1.47E-06	1.48E-06	1.50E-06	1.53E-06	1.57E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	2.92E-09	2.93E-09	2.94E-09	2.95E-09	2.97E-09	3.00E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.48E-05	4.48E-05	4.50E-05	4.51E-05	4.53E-05	4.56E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	5.49E-04	5.49E-04	5.50E-04	5.50E-04	5.51E-04	5.52E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	3.19E-04	3.20E-04	3.22E-04	3.23E-04	3.26E-04	3.29E-04	molc N eq

Water resource depletion	2.75E-02	2.77E-02	2.79E-02	2.83E-02	2.87E-02	2.93E-02	m ³ water eq
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Table S5 part 3: Life cycle impacts of the Mg-S EV under different efficiency, electricity and energy density scenarios. (ED = Energy density).

Overall efficiency = 0.8							
Category	Electricity DE2030						Unit
	100%ED (Baseline)	90%ED	80%ED	70%ED	60%ED	50%ED	
Acidification	2.90E-04	2.92E-04	2.94E-04	2.97E-04	3.02E-04	3.07E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	9.75E-02	9.83E-02	9.92E-02	1.00E-01	1.02E-01	1.04E-01	kg CO2 eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	2.96E+00	2.98E+00	3.01E+00	3.05E+00	3.10E+00	3.18E+00	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophication	8.03E-05	8.10E-05	8.18E-05	8.29E-05	8.44E-05	8.65E-05	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	9.75E-09	9.82E-09	9.92E-09	1.00E-08	1.02E-08	1.04E-08	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	3.25E-08	3.27E-08	3.30E-08	3.34E-08	3.39E-08	3.46E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	1.08E-08	1.08E-08	1.08E-08	1.09E-08	1.09E-08	1.10E-08	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	2.55E-03	2.56E-03	2.57E-03	2.58E-03	2.60E-03	2.63E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	2.02E-01	2.03E-01	2.04E-01	2.05E-01	2.06E-01	2.08E-01	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	7.51E-05	7.55E-05	7.61E-05	7.69E-05	7.79E-05	7.94E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.73E-06	1.74E-06	1.76E-06	1.78E-06	1.81E-06	1.85E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	6.07E-09	6.11E-09	6.15E-09	6.21E-09	6.28E-09	6.39E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	5.19E-05	5.20E-05	5.22E-05	5.24E-05	5.27E-05	5.31E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	6.42E-04	6.43E-04	6.45E-04	6.47E-04	6.49E-04	6.53E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	6.85E-04	6.89E-04	6.94E-04	7.01E-04	7.10E-04	7.22E-04	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	5.37E-02	5.42E-02	5.47E-02	5.53E-02	5.62E-02	5.74E-02	m ³ water eq

Table S5 part 4: Life cycle impacts of the Mg-S EV under different efficiency, electricity and energy density scenarios. (ED = Energy density).

Overall efficiency = 0.8							
Category	Electricity RN						Unit
	100%ED (Baseline)	90%ED	80%ED	70%ED	60%ED	50%ED	
Acidification	1.45E-04	1.45E-04	1.46E-04	1.47E-04	1.48E-04	1.50E-04	molc H+ eq
Climate change	2.21E-02	2.22E-02	2.23E-02	2.25E-02	2.27E-02	2.29E-02	kg CO2 eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	1.13E+00	1.13E+00	1.14E+00	1.16E+00	1.18E+00	1.20E+00	CTUe

Freshwater eutrophication	8.55E-06	8.59E-06	8.65E-06	8.72E-06	8.82E-06	8.96E-06	kg P eq
Human toxicity, cancer effects	5.49E-09	5.53E-09	5.57E-09	5.63E-09	5.70E-09	5.81E-09	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	1.29E-08	1.29E-08	1.30E-08	1.31E-08	1.32E-08	1.34E-08	CTUh
Ionizing radiation E (interim)	1.04E-08	1.05E-08	1.05E-08	1.05E-08	1.06E-08	1.07E-08	CTUe
Ionizing radiation HH	2.39E-03	2.39E-03	2.40E-03	2.42E-03	2.43E-03	2.45E-03	kBq U235 eq
Land use	1.18E+00	1.19E+00	1.20E+00	1.22E+00	1.24E+00	1.27E+00	kg C deficit
Marine eutrophication	3.39E-05	3.40E-05	3.41E-05	3.43E-05	3.45E-05	3.49E-05	kg N eq
Mineral, fossil & ren resource depletion	1.68E-06	1.69E-06	1.71E-06	1.73E-06	1.75E-06	1.79E-06	kg Sb eq
Ozone depletion	3.08E-09	3.09E-09	3.10E-09	3.11E-09	3.13E-09	3.16E-09	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate matter	4.63E-05	4.64E-05	4.65E-05	4.67E-05	4.69E-05	4.71E-05	kg PM2.5 eq
Photochemical ozone formation	5.55E-04	5.56E-04	5.56E-04	5.57E-04	5.58E-04	5.59E-04	kg NMVOC eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	3.39E-04	3.40E-04	3.41E-04	3.43E-04	3.45E-04	3.49E-04	molc N eq
Water resource depletion	3.12E-02	3.14E-02	3.17E-02	3.20E-02	3.25E-02	3.31E-02	m3 water eq

Life Cycle Inventories

Mg-S Electric Vehicles (Mg-S EV)

Table S5: LCI of 1 km driven with a Mg-S EV. All parameters adopt a value of either 1 or 0 according to the respective scenario.

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
electricity, low voltage	$\left(\frac{\text{combined} * 0.142 + \text{city} * 0.11 + \text{highway} * 0.181}{\text{batt_eff_factor}}\right) - (0.00178 * \text{baselineMgS}) - (0.0002128 * \text{ED90}) + (0.0017472 * \text{ED80}) + (0.0042672 * \text{ED70}) + (0.0076216 * \text{ED60}) + (0.0123256 * \text{ED50}) * \text{DE}_{2030}$	kWh	2030 market for electricity, low voltage (Table S18)
Electricity, renewable mix	$\left(\frac{\text{combined} * 0.142 + \text{city} * 0.11 + \text{highway} * 0.181}{\text{batt_eff_factor}}\right) - (0.00178 * \text{baselineMgS}) - (0.0002128 * \text{ED90}) + (0.0017472 * \text{ED80}) + (0.0042672 * \text{ED70}) + (0.0076216 * \text{ED60}) + (0.0123256 * \text{ED50}) * \text{renew}$	kWh	Electricity, renewable mix 50-50 (Table S15)
maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery	6.67E-06	Item(s)	market for maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery Cutoff, U - GLO
road	4.87E-04	m*a	market for road road Cutoff, U - GLO
road maintenance	1.17E-03	m*a	market for road maintenance road

			maintenance Cutoff, U - RER
Outputs			
transport, passenger car, Mg-S EV	1.00E+00	km	
brake wear emissions, passenger car	1.05E-06	kg	market for brake wear emissions, passenger car brake wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
road wear emissions, passenger car	1.16E-05	kg	market for road wear emissions, passenger car road wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
tyre wear emissions, passenger car	6.76E-05	kg	market for tyre wear emissions, passenger car tyre wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO

Table S6: LCI of manufacturing 1 kg Mg-S battery pack. Adapted from [1]

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	2.52E-02	kg	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB [2]
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	4.10E-02	kg	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack [2]
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	1.27E-01	kg	Battery packaging, for Li-Ion battery (Table S8)
MgScell	6.13E-01	kg	MgScell (Table S7)
Module packaging, for Li-Ion battery pack	1.93E-01	kg	Module packaging, for Li-Ion battery (Table S9)
precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)	market for precious metal refinery precious metal refinery Cutoff, U - GLO
transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	1.60E-01	t*km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cutoff, U - RER
transport, freight, sea, container ship	4.90E+00	t*km	market for transport, freight, sea, container ship transport, freight, sea, container ship Cutoff, U - GLO
Outputs			
MgS_battery_pack	1	kg	

Table S7: LCI of manufacturing 1 kg Mg-S cell. Extracted from [3]

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Anode_MgScell	2.90E-01	kg	Anode_MgScell_Evo2 [3]
Cathode_MgScell	3.50E-01	kg	Cathode_MgScell_Evo2 [3]
electrolyte v2	3.10E-01	kg	Electrolyte_0.3M_MgS_Evo2 [3]
Housing_Mgcell	3.00E-02	kg	Housing_MgS_Evo2 [3]
Separator_Mgcell	2.00E-02	kg	Separator_MgS_Evo2 [3]
Outputs			
MgScell	1	kg	

Table S8: LCI of battery pack housing, adapted from [1]

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Battery retention, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	1.10E-01	kg	Battery retention, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
Battery tray, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	3.00E-01	kg	Battery tray, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	1.50E-01	t*km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cutoff, U - RER
transport, freight, sea, container ship	4.80E+00	t*km	market for transport, freight, sea, container ship transport, freight, sea, container ship Cutoff, U - GLO
Outputs			
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	1	kg	

Table S9: LCI of battery module packaging, adapted from [1]

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Aluminium endbars, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery	1.60E-03	kg	Aluminium endbars, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
Bimetallic busbars and washers, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery	3.40E-02	kg	Bimetallic busbars and washers, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
Copper end-busbars, for module packaging, Li->Ion battery	4.90E-03	kg	Copper end-busbars, for module packaging, Li->Ion battery [2]
Module fasteners, for battery module packing, Li-Ion	4.80E-02	kg	Module fasteners, for battery module packing, Li-Ion [2]
Module lid, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery	2.80E-02	kg	Module lid, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
Outer frame, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery	8.80E-01	kg	Outer frame, for module packaging, Li-Ion battery [2]
precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)	market for precious metal refinery precious metal refinery Cutoff, U - GLO
transport, freight train	2.00E-01	t*km	market for transport, freight train transport, freight train Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland
transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	1.00E-01	t*km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cutoff, U - RER
Outputs			
Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Module packaging, for Li-Ion battery pack	1	kg	

LIB Electric Vehicles (LIB EV)

Table S10: LCI of 1 km driven with a LIB EV. All parameters adopt a value either 1 or 0 according to the respective scenario.

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
electricity, DE2030	$(\text{combined} * 0.142 + \text{city} * 0.11 + \text{highway} * 0.181) * \text{DE_2030}$	kWh	Electricity DE2030 mix low voltage (Table S18)
Electricity, renewable mix	$(\text{combined} * 0.142 + \text{city} * 0.11 + \text{highway} * 0.181) * \text{renew}$	kWh	Electricity, renewable mix 50-50 (Table S15)
maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery	6.67E-06	Item(s)	market for maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery maintenance, passenger car, electric, without battery Cutoff, U - GLO
road	4.87E-04	m*a	market for road road Cutoff, U - GLO
road maintenance	0.00117	m*a	market for road maintenance road maintenance Cutoff, U - RER
Outputs			
brake wear emissions, passenger car	1.05E-06	kg	market for brake wear emissions, passenger car brake wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
road wear emissions, passenger car	1.16E-05	kg	market for road wear emissions, passenger car road wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
transport, passenger car, electric	1.00E+00	km	
tyre wear emissions, passenger car	6.76E-05	kg	market for tyre wear emissions, passenger car tyre wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO

Table S11: LCI of manufacturing 1 kg LIB NMC (811) pack. Adapted from [1]

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Battery cell storage capacity (Chordia)	1.41E+02	Wh	Battery cell storage capacity generation [4]
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	2.52E-02	kg	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB [2]
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	4.10E-02	kg	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack [2]
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	1.27E-01	kg	Battery packaging, for Li-Ion battery (Table S8)
Module packaging, for Li-Ion battery pack	1.93E-01	kg	Module packaging, for Li-Ion battery (Table S9)
precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)	market for precious metal refinery precious metal refinery Cutoff, U - GLO
transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	1.60E-01	t*km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cutoff, U - RER
transport, freight, sea, container ship	4.90E+00	t*km	market for transport, freight, sea, container ship transport, freight, sea, container ship Cutoff, U - GLO
Outputs			
Li-Ion battery pack, NCM 811	1	kg	

Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles (ICEV)

Table S12: LCI of 1 km driven with an ICEV. All parameters adopt a value either 1 or 0 according to the respective scenario
Adapted from Ecoinvent 3.8..

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Biodiesel B100	$B100 * (\text{combined} * 0.03948 + \text{city} * 0.05544 + \text{highway} * 0.0336) / 0.93$	kg	Biodiesel B100 (Table S14)
Biodiesel B20	$B20 * (\text{combined} * 0.03948 + \text{city} * 0.05544 + \text{highway} * 0.0336) / 0.99$	kg	Biodiesel B20 (Table S13)
diesel, low-sulfur	$\text{Fossil_Diesel} * (\text{combined} * 0.03948 + \text{city} * 0.05544 + \text{highway} * 0.0336)$	kg	market group for diesel, low-sulfur diesel, low-sulfur Cutoff, U - RER
passenger car maintenance	8.60E-06	Item(s)	maintenance, passenger car passenger car maintenance Cutoff, U - RER
refrigerant R134a	4.99E-06	kg	refrigerant R134a production refrigerant R134a Cutoff, U - RER
road	8.04E-04	m*a	market for road road Cutoff, U - GLO
road maintenance	0.00117	m*a	market for road maintenance road maintenance Cutoff, U - RER
Outputs (adapted from [5])			
transport, passenger car, medium size, diesel, EURO 6	1	km	
Acetaldehyde	7.12E-07	kg	
Acetone	3.24E-07	kg	
Acrolein	3.94E-07	kg	
Ammonia	1.00E-06	kg	
Arsenic	4.07E-12	kg	
Benzaldehyde	9.47E-08	kg	
Benzene	2.18E-07	kg	
brake wear emissions, passenger car	7.55E-06	kg	market for brake wear emissions, passenger car brake wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
Butane	1.21E-08	kg	
Cadmium	3.54E-10	kg	
Carbon dioxide, fossil	1.29E-01	kg	
Carbon monoxide, fossil	5.24E-05	kg	
Chromium	1.22E-09	kg	
Chromium IV	2.44E-12	kg	
Copper	8.62E-10	kg	
Cyclohexane (for all cycloalkanes)	7.16E-08	kg	
Dinitrogen monoxide	4.67E-06	kg	
Ethane	3.63E-08	kg	
Ethane, 1,1,1,2-tetrafluoro-, HFC-134a	4.99E-06	kg	
Ethene	1.21E-06	kg	
Formaldehyde	1.32E-06	kg	
Heptane	2.20E-08	kg	
Lead	2.12E-09	kg	
m-Xylene	6.72E-08	kg	
Mercury	2.16E-10	kg	

Methane	2.71E-07	kg	
Methyl ethyl ketone	1.32E-07	kg	
Nickel	3.58E-10	kg	
Nitrogen oxides	2.59E-04	kg	
NMVOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds, unspecified origin	5.84E-06	kg	
Noise, road, passenger car, average	8.04E-04	m	
o-Xylene	2.97E-08	kg	
PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	3.12E-09	kg	
Particulates, < 2.5 um	2.03E-06	kg	
Pentane	4.40E-09	kg	
Propane	1.21E-08	kg	
Propene	3.96E-07	kg	
road wear emissions, passenger car	1.66E-05	kg	market for road wear emissions, passenger car road wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
Selenium	4.07E-12	kg	
Styrene	4.07E-08	kg	
Sulfur dioxide	6.51E-07	kg	
Toluene	7.60E-08	kg	
tyre wear emissions, passenger car	9.72E-05	kg	market for tyre wear emissions, passenger car tyre wear emissions, passenger car Cutoff, U - GLO
Zinc	7.07E-08	kg	

Energy carriers

Table S13: LCI of B20 biodiesel

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
diesel, low-sulfur	0.8	kg	market for diesel, low-sulfur diesel, low-sulfur Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland
fatty acid methyl ester	0.2	kg	market for vegetable oil methyl ester vegetable oil methyl ester Cutoff, U - GLO
Outputs			
Biodiesel B20	1	kg	

Table S14: LCI of B100 biodiesel

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
fatty acid methyl ester	1	kg	market for vegetable oil methyl ester vegetable oil methyl ester Cutoff, U - GLO
Outputs			
Biodiesel B20	1	kg	

Table S15: LCI of electricity mix RN

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
electricity, high voltage	0.5	kWh	electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, low voltage	0.5	kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si electricity, low voltage Cutoff, U - DE
Outputs			
Electricity, renewable mix 50-50	1	kWh	

Table S16: LCI of electricity mix DE2030, high voltage

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
electricity, high voltage	0.010	kWh	electricity production, hydro, pumped storage electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.003	kWh	heat and power co-generation, natural gas, combined cycle power plant, 400MW electrical electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.116	kWh	electricity production, lignite electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.036	kWh	electricity production, wind, <1MW turbine, onshore electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.151	kWh	electricity production, hard coal electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.019	kWh	heat and power co-generation, hard coal electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.041	kWh	heat and power co-generation, biogas, gas engine electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.010	kWh	heat and power co-generation, wood chips, 6667 kW, state-of-the-art 2014 electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.002	kWh	electricity production, oil electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.022	kWh	electricity production, wind, >3MW turbine, onshore electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.171	kWh	heat and power co-generation, natural gas, conventional power plant, 100MW electrical electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.127	kWh	electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbine, offshore electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.002	kWh	electricity production, deep geothermal electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.198	kWh	electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.000	kWh	heat and power co-generation, oil electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.005	kWh	electricity production, hydro, reservoir, non-alpine region electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.007	kWh	treatment of coal gas, in power plant electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.026	kWh	electricity production, hydro, run-of-river electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.033	kWh	electricity production, natural gas, combined cycle power plant electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.003	kWh	heat and power co-generation, lignite electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, high voltage	0.020	kWh	electricity production, natural gas, conventional power plant electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U - DE
Outputs			

Electricity DE2030 mix, high voltage	1	kWh	
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Table S17: LCI of electricity mix DE2030, medium voltage

Inputs			
Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
electricity, medium voltage	2.42E-02	kWh	electricity, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, medium voltage	9.76E-01	kWh	Electricity DE2030 mix, high voltage (Table S16)
Outputs			
Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Electricity DE2030 mix, medium voltage	1	kWh	

Table S18: LCI of electricity mix DE2030, low voltage

Flow	Amount	Unit	Provider
Inputs			
Electricity from PV (updt)	2.97E-02	kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si electricity, low voltage Cutoff, U - DE
Electricity from PV (updt)	4.77E-02	kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted electricity, low voltage Cutoff, U - DE
Electricity from PV (updt)	3.83E-02	kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, single-Si, panel, mounted electricity, low voltage Cutoff, U - DE
electricity, low voltage	8.84E-01	kWh	Electricity DE2030 mix, medium voltage (Table S17)
Outputs			
Electricity DE2030 mix, low voltage	1	kWh	

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